

Contemporary Architecture Design through Bionic fractal:

An approach of integrated Bionic Fractal geometry

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ABSTRACT

The paper intensive about the modern approaches of bionic fractal towards architecture design inspiration. An investigation of the translation and application of theoretical & conceptual ideas from fractal geometry of plants and humans body. These all possibilities are presence in nature recourses like human cells, plant typical structure. Contextual mimicry of nature can be used as a tool of inspiration in design & development process of an architecture project. Each borrowed concepts are considered in both its originative and architectural context. Alternative critical views toward the

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possibilities and role of copying in architecture are proposed and discussed. The objectives to explore the prospective inspiration for architecture design as the essential element of concept to theorize, analyze, and generate new ideas through bionic fractal. These all practice based approaches explore incipient conceptual trends in contemporary architecture design edification & preparation as well as for the emerging sustainable imminent--fabricated environs for our society.

Key Words: Deconstructive architecture, Bionic fractal geometry, contemporary architecture.

1. Introduction

Bionic fractal, assumption, reconceptualization, and displacement might each be active, depending upon one's perspective, to describe the shifting of advanced structures of thought developed in one disciplinary context to alternative. As an intelligible body of thought, the copied structure often brings with it its own vocabulary, adherents, and critics. Tension often develops between the initiates and those previously unaware of the new position and its terminology. The confusion, excitement, and opportunity generated by the recent introduction in architecture of ideas associated with the philosophic movement known as deconstruction make this a particularly appropriate moment to review the environments of biology and fractal. This study will focus on approaches and method of accepting biological and fractal intervention, in which links to deconstruction, microbiological processes, and fractal geometry are all explicitly acknowledged in a detailed descriptive text, as a vehicle for this exploration. A double articulation interpreting both biological and architectural

conditions geometrically, in the process "deconstructing" the conventional assumptions surrounding them to create "a project that is neither simply architectural nor simply biological, but one suspended between the two." The references to deconstruction, molecular biology and the fractal geometric operations will each be considered in the contexts of both their source and their architectural indexes. [1] The evidence thus gathered will be considered in its impact upon the possible evolution of attitudes toward deriving in architecture design.

2. Discussion

Deconstruction and architecture design really came into close contact through a number of architectural conferences at the Tate in London and at MOMA in New York in 1988. Many of the brightest contemporary architects of the 1980's were involved with these events including Peter Eisenman, Frank Gehry, Zaha Hadid, Coop Himmelblau, Rem

Koolhaas, Daniel Libeskind, Bernard Tschumi. In 'Deconstruction' the major anthology following these events, Andreas Papidakis writes '*Few ideas in architecture have created such a stir as Deconstruction in the relatively short time since it gained currency and public prominence*' [2].

The aim of this paper is to find ways of engaging with deconstruction through fractal intervention that have a utility beyond academic design philosophy. attempting to be direct and straightforward while acknowledging that even using the term deconstruction establishes a binary relationship (inside/outside deconstruction) that is potentially problematic and can be regarded as creating a deconstructive orthodoxy through categorization.

'Deconstruction is that which is necessary to structure but evades structural analysis (and analysis is invariably structural). It is the breakdown of structure that is the very possibility of structure' [3]

3. Deconstruction and Contemporary Architecture Design Theory

One of the principal aspects of the Post-modern rejection of the modernist point of view was the shift from social theory to literary theory as the paradigm for architectural theory. Robert Venturi, in his book *Complexity and Contradiction in Architecture* used the literary criticism of T. S. Eliot as a framework for analyzing architecture. Eliot had pointed out that poetry is captivating because it is not univalent and clear but multivalent and layered, filled with many possible readings and interpretations, i.e. "complex and contradictory". Literary criticism, however, was not the only source of new architectural thinking in the 1970s and 1980s. Morphological theory also rose to prominence as an apparatus for understanding architecture. [4]

architectural critics and academics: deconstruction. The principal inventor of literary deconstruction was Jacques Derrida, a French linguist, who argued that meaning in language is completely unstable. He argued that a text cannot have any single meaning, certainly not a meaning that the writer invests in it.

A number of architects whose work came to international prominence in the 1980s have either been interested in some version of literary theory or have

been described as representing the general directions of linguistic theory. These include, but are not limited to, Peter Eisenman, Wolf Prix of the firm Coop Himmelblau in Vienna, Guenther Behnisch, Frank Gehry, (Figure 1) and Zaha Hadid, the Iraqi-born British architect, currently building the new Contemporary Art Center in Cincinnati. (Figure 2) [5]

"Deconstruction has grasped the point that the binary oppositions with which classical structuralism tends to work represents a way of seeing typical of ideologies. Ideologies like to draw rigid boundaries between what is acceptable and what is not, between self and non-self, truth and falsity, reason and madness, central and marginal such metaphysical thinking cannot be simply eluded: we cannot catapult ourselves beyond this binary habit of thought into an ultra-metaphysical realm. [6]

Figure 1: Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao, Spain

Figure 2: Contemporary Art Center in Cincinnati

4. Bionic Fractal Intervention in Architectural Design

The role of bionic fractal geometry in the process of design: "To accomplish this departed from the traditional representation of biology by making an architectural reading of the biological concepts of DNA and internal structure processes by interpreting

them in terms of geometrical process. At the same time, departed from the traditional representation of architecture by abandoning the classical unbalance geometry on which the discipline is based in favor of bionic fractal geometry." There is a sliding of meaning here which is most curious and somewhat casual with respect to both mathematics and geometry.

Bionic fractal geometry concerns itself with geometric descriptions of the complex fragmentations of edges, as in clouds, mountains, coastlines, of bionic deep structure in organic form. Their key property is self-similarity, or invariance with respect to scale, and they are considered to be different from the true bionic structured solids and forms.

Fractal form which is defined as "geometry based on the three-dimensional space of experience". The strange demands placed upon bionic fractal geometry are better understood when considered in the context of the deconstructive intentions of this project, particularly the undermining of "presence". [7]

Figure 3: Olympic complex structure

Figure 4: Museum of natural arts

The use of bionic fractal geometry as a system to define complex and fragmentary forms is problematic in the light of both deconstructions which warns us to suspect the origin of any system, and in light of extremely complex forms found, for example, in vernacular architecture or urban plans both of which continue to be well documented in the "geometry of experience".

The aspect missing in these examples and supplied by bionic fractal geometry is the generative. It appears that bionic fractal geometry not only describes the undermining of presence, but is also the generator of it. [8]

5. Method & Approaches

Biological reproduction, there is a tremendous range of bionic fractal exploration, a significant portion of which is directed toward the exploration of methods of representing complex three-dimensional natural forms through the use of mathematically generated graphics. The issue of choice and taste is again unavoidable.

The use of bionic geometrical operations as a source of form is paralleled in the consideration of deconstruction not as a critical bionic structure, but as a generative structure. Some deconstructions would advise that works of criticism are creative enterprises in their own right, and the critical /generative split is a false one, designed to "keep deconstruction in its place." Certainly works of deconstructive criticism are creative, and many have their own strong character, but the process of deconstruction demands the existence of elements whose flaws it can then demonstrate. How are these elements to be produced?

Answer is that these elements are to be geometricized representations of programmatic or associational meaning. The limitations of this approach to either architecture or the application principles from deconstruction are obvious. Although all architecture is reducible to geometric descriptions of its physicality, geometric variation, particularly of a systematic biological in nature, does not necessarily produce architectural meaning. It is hard not to conclude that it has associated presence in architecture with the conventional geometry of building and therefore feels that presence can be undermined by the altering of this fractal geometry. [9]

6. Attitude towards Methodology & test sample

"The influence of the allied biology on architectural design raises ethical problems of considerable gravity, for what this influence can bring about, and undoubtedly has brought about, certain benefits, it can also vitiate the nature of architectural creativity by leading to the production of forms which are not strictly architectural at all. But it seems nevertheless fair to say that when the allied biology have exerted an excessive or even predominant influence on architectural design, the result has often been virtual architecture, (Figure 5-9)

Figure 5: Biological algorithm structure & Atrium of British museum

Figure 6 & 7 : Neurological mapping

Figure 8: Retina deep structure

Figure 9: Bionic tower skin detail

in the sense that it is difficult in such instances to tell where the genuine tectonic virtues [emphasis added] of the work are to be found... But if the artistic merit of a building depends mainly on literary romantic allusions, it may be reasonably argued that such buildings are not architecture at all but whimsically conceived constructions disguised in the copied aesthetic trappings of another similar structure." From a deconstructive point of view, context is dripping with ties to assumed metaphysical authority. Its refers, without definition or clarification, to "forms which are not strictly architectural" may be more bionic structural based. (Figure 10) Clearly there is an assumed, and privileged condition of "being architectural form," which the particular production he is criticizing is outside. This is an effort to draw a boundary, but the words do not define one, rather forcing us to assume it through our own explanation of the word "architectural bionic deconstruction". [10]

Figure 10: Various Architectural façades skins

7. Application and Implementation (Example)

7.1 Vertical Habitation (Tower)

The intention of the Bionic Tower is to explore the array of ways in which natural and architectural can merge, creating the ultimate inhabitable structure. It starts at the basic level. Using references to the biological organization (Figure 12-15) of the ecosystem, the design works its way from the smallest unit to the intelligence of the overall system. By use of parametric modeling of a behavioral logic the system gets constantly optimized. Designed by LAVA, [12] this biomorphic project is inspired by nature, and attempts to conceive a structure of great lightness, efficiency and elegance, using advanced design techniques. The architects seem to address issues of ventilation, solar access and water collection as an evolutionary instinct of self-preservation, found in nature and adopted by architecture. Envisioned as equivalents to mechanisms of organic regeneration, the proposed systems are connected to the facade design. They are embedded in the façade in the form of intelligent automation of the surfaces, addressing pragmatic issues such as ventilation, solar access and water collection. New materials and technologies enable adaptability, responsiveness, environmental awareness and strength. The building systems and skin are controlled and react to external influences like air pressure, temperature, humidity, air pollution and solar radiation. [4]

Figure 11-12: Tower detail

Figure 13-14: Bionic inspired architectural skin geometry

Figure 15: Bionic skin geometry detail

7.2 Bionic inspired complex design

Project designed by Arthur Azoulai and Melody Rees is a morphological study that assumes an extended field of movement and circulating forces. It is designed by simulating self-organizing biological systems where selective decision making is used to sculpt innate yet deliberate spatial relationships and formal qualities. At its pure essence, this project is an infrastructural system that acts as a receiver and link-up for formal architectural systems. (Figure 16) The inherent continuity of the overall form as a topological surface allows for the emergence of roadways, interstitial interior space, and landscape. [11]

Figure 16: Section showing internal structure

Figure 17 : Bionic inspired complex design

With imbricating structural support (*Figure 18*) systems, the collective tectonics provide a network of circulation paths for pedestrians, cars and trams in addition to an emphasis on temporary pavilion spaces such as transitory food markets, pop-up retail shops and time-share housing. With a temporal and ephemeral program, the local culture of stature in San Juan becomes active. Correspondingly, the adaptive qualities of the infrastructural surface allow the building and site form an organic semiotic relationship where the building seamlessly emerges from the land below. This is emphasized as the ecologically evasive character of Puerto Rico's environment merges into the architecture.

Figure 18: Fractal geometry based building structure

8. CONCLUSION

Biological structure had to take a leap into bionic geometry, or dispersed life regroups in the genetic code and forms. Dispersed work had to regroup in third-generation machines, cybernetics and information technology. What would be the forces in play, with which the forces within man would then enter into a relation? It would no longer involve rising to infinity or finitude but an unlimited finite, thereby evoking every situation of force in which a finite number of components yields a practically unlimited diversity of combinations. It would be neither the fold nor the unfold that would constitute the active tool, but something like the Super fold, as borne out by the folding's proper to the chains of the genomic code, and the potential of biology in third-generation technologies, as well as by the contours of a sentence in contemporary architecture, when form 'just turns back on itself in an endless reflexivity. We have attempted in this paper to plan a small section of a similar intervention of the bionic fractal and development for architectural design as contemporary endless possibilities. In our way, the bionic fractal is inscribed in the fluid lines of flight of architectural design processes that cut across and inflect not only

architecture and bioinformatics, but also interdisciplinary.

9. REFERENCES

- [1]. Peter Eisenman, "Biology Center for the J.W. Goethe University of Frankfurt, Frankfurt am Main, 1987," *Assemblage* 5, February 1988: 30.
- [2]. Jacques Derrida, "Letter to a Japanese Friend," *Derrida and Difference*, ed. David Wood (Evanston: Northwestern UP, 1988) The letter is dated 10 July 1983.
- [3]. Maxim D. Frank-Kamenetskii, "DNA Supercoiling and Unusual Structures," *DNA Topology and its Biological Effects*, Nicholas R. Cozzarelli and James Wang eds. (Cold Spring Harbor, NY: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory P, 1990) 185.
- [4]. Cyrus Levinthal, "Molecular Model-Building by Computer," *Scientific American*, Vol. 214, no. 6, 1966, pp. 42-52.
- [5]. Eisenman's early embrace of postmodern approaches, see Peter Eisenman, "Cardboard Architecture: House I (1967), in Peter Eisenman, Michael Graves, Charles Gwathmey, John Hedjuk, Richard Meier, Collin Rowe, and Kenneth Frampton, *Five Architects*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 1975), pp. 15-23, and Eisenman, "Cardboard Architecture: House II (1969)," *Five Architects*, pp. 25-37.
- [6]. <http://www.archmorpho.us/2012/06/bionic-tower-combines-structure-and.html>
- [7]. <http://www.xiols.us/architecture/architecture-designed-to-simulate-self-organizing-biological-systems/>
- [8]. <http://www.seattlepi.com/ae/article/San-Francisco-s-renovated-Conservatory-of-Flowers-1119670.php>
- [9]. <http://www.rpi.edu/about/inside/issue/v6n2/empac.html>
- [10]. <http://www.suckerpunchdaily.com/2012/04/09/cathedral-of-our-lady-of-the-angels-based-on-bionics/>
- [11]. <http://www.pbo.ds.mpg.de/Research.html>
- [12]. <http://www.l-a-v-a.net>

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